

Effect of mobile phase composition and pH on thin layer chromatographic behaviour of amino acids

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The chromatographic behaviour of twentyfour amino acids has been studied on plain silica gel-G layers in one-component, two-component (butanol-acetic acid) and three-component (acetone-benzene-acetic acid) mobile phases in varying ratios. The effects of pH and composition of the mobile phase and also of the mole fraction of each component on R_F values are discussed. The mechanism of migration is explained in terms of adsorption on silica gel-G and the polarity of the mobile phase.

A literature survey reveals planar layer chromatography of amino acids on impregnated¹ and modified² silica gel-G layers, but no work has been reported on plain silica gel-G, the layers of which are inexpensive and very easy to prepare and give compact spots. Recently emphasis is given on OPTLC and HPTLC separation of amino acids³. However, all these studies suffer from various limitations.

In view of the above facts, we have decided to study the thin layer chromatographic behaviour of 24 amino acids on plain silica gel-G layers in butanol-acetic acid and acetone-benzene-acetic acid media. Butanol was chosen owing to our earlier experience⁴. Butanol-acetic acid media was taken as it effected a large number of amino acid separations on titanium arsenate papers⁵.

Results and Discussion

The chromatographic behaviour of the amino acids was studied in one-, two- and three-component mobile phases and some useful separations were carried out. The spots are very compact and no tailing is observed. To check the reproducibility of the results, three sets of plates were developed for each amino acid. Variation in R_F did not exceed 5% of the average value.

One-component mobile phases :

The chromatographic behaviour of amino acids in one-component mobile phases such as methanol, ethanol, butanol, propanol-2, benzene, acetic acid, acetone and DMW (demineralized water) was studied. For majority of amino acids, the R_F values are relatively much higher (>0.50) in acetic acid and DMW in comparison to other mobile phases, probably due to the polar nature of acetic acid and DMW in which the amino acids are more soluble.

For DL-DOPA (dihydroxyphenylalanine), the R_F value is relatively much lower in acetic acid media thereby showing

an exceptional behaviour. This may be due to strong adsorption of DL-DOPA on silica gel-G layers. As a result the separation of DL-DOPA from all other neutral, basic and acidic amino acids have actually been realized on these layers.

In methanol, the basic amino acids such as L-ornithine HCl, L-lysine HCl, L-histidine HCl and L-arginine have almost zero R_F value. This is due to the presence of an extra NH_2 group having an extra lone-pair of electrons. Silica gel may, therefore, have a greater affinity for such a molecule as compared to acidic and neutral amino acids. Similarly DL-aspartic acid, L-proline and L-tyrosine also have zero R_F probably due to their higher adsorption on these layers and can be separated from other amino acids. However, S-containing amino acids such as L-cystine have lower R_F and its separation from other S-containing amino acids, i.e. L-cysteine HCl, and DL-methionine have actually been achieved.

Two-component mobile phases (butanol-acetic acid) :

Butanol-acetic acid mixture in different ratios proved to be an excellent mobile phase for a number of amino acid separations.

Effect of mobile phase composition on the retention behaviour of amino acids : Plots of R_F vs butanol-acetic acid proportions are quite revealing. In pure butanol, it is observed that for almost all neutral amino acids except L-cysteine HCl, L-cystine, and L-glycine, there is a significant intercept on y-axis showing thereby that all these neutral amino acids are soluble in butanol to different extent. Although we do not have the solubility data of neutral amino acids in butanol, yet the intercept gives a rough measure of their solubility. On the basis of R_F data, the solubility sequence of amino acids in butanol may be given as follows : DL- β -phenylalanine > DL-tryptophan > L-tyrosine > DL-methionine > DL-DOPA > DL-2-aminobutyric acid > DL-

alanine > L-leucine > DL-valine > DL-nor-leucine > DL-threonine > DL-serine > DL-isoleucine > L-hydroxyproline > L-proline.

The R_F values, in general, increase with an increase in acetic acid content. It is known that amino acids are less soluble in butanol than in acetic acid. The presence of an increased amount of acetic acid facilitates the partition of the solute in mobile phase and hence an increase in the R_F value is expected. Interestingly, L-hydroxyproline and L-cysteine HCl show irregular behaviour.

In case of amino acids having aliphatic side chain such as L-leucine, DL-valine, DL-alanine, and L-glycine the R_F values in the mobile phases having composition 7 : 3 and 8 : 2, show the following migration sequence : L-leucine > DL-valine > DL-alanine > L-glycine. In these cases, the R_F value is directly proportional to the size of aliphatic side-chain. The same trend was also observed in case of heterocyclic neutral amino acids : DL-tryptophan > L-hydroxyproline > L-proline. This migration behaviour is quite in agreement with the earlier observations on cellulose phosphate papers⁶. Neutral simple amino acids, i.e. L-glycine, DL-alanine, DL-valine, L-leucine, DL-isoleucine and DL-nor-leucine also exhibit the same trend. This agrees well with the earlier observation made by Nabi *et al.*⁷ that there is an increase in R_F value with an increase in the molecular weight of amino acids. On the other hand, all the S-containing amino acids show a mixed trend.

From the above discussion, it is concluded that the maximum possibilities for binary and ternary amino acid separations occur in butanol-acetic acid mobile phases having compositions 7 : 3, 8 : 2 and 9 : 1.

All the basic amino acids, i.e. L-ornithine HCl, L-lysine HCl, L-histidine HCl and L-arginine have lower R_F values than the neutral and acidic amino acids particularly when the mobile phase composition lies between 9 : 1 and 5 : 5.

Effect of mobile phase pH on the retention behaviour of amino acids : (i) For neutral and acidic amino acids : The plots of R_F vs pH reveal that the R_F is generally higher and remains almost constant in pH range 0.0–1.0. It is probably due to the amino acids being present in the cationic form in presence of H^+ ion. On further increase in pH, R_F gradually decreases and becomes less than 0.2 at pH 6.74. This can be explained as that when the pH is increased beyond 1.0, the cationic form of the amino acids starts changing into the zwitterionic form which is probably more strongly adsorbed on silica gel-G layers resulting in a gradual decrease in R_F . (ii) For basic amino acids : At low pH (<0.02), R_F values lie between 0.6 and 0.8. On increasing the pH there is a sharp decrease in R_F which becomes less than 0.2 at pH 0.6 except for L-histidine which gives higher R_F . It is probably due to the rapid transition of cationic form to the zwitterionic form resulting in a decrease in R_F .

Three-component mobile phases (acetone-benzene-acetic acid) :

R_F vs mole fractions of acetone, benzene and acetic acid were studied and the effect of various components of the mobile phase used is discussed below.

Effect of mole fraction of acetone : For most of the amino acids, the R_F values slightly decrease with increase in the mole fraction of acetone in acetone-benzene-acetic acid media having volume ratios 5 : 1 : 4, 6 : 1 : 3, 7 : 1 : 2 and 8 : 1 : 1. The exceptions being L-lysine HCl, L-ornithine HCl, L-histidine, L-arginine and L-proline, which exhibit an increase in the R_F till the mole fraction of acetone becomes 0.57. On further increase in the mole fraction of acetone upto 0.69, the R_F values decrease. Beyond this, the R_F remain almost constant except for L-proline which surprisingly shows a sharp increase.

DL-Valine, DL-serine, L-glycine and L-cysteine HCl exhibit a different trend as the R_F values initially decrease until the mole fraction of acetone in the mixture attains a certain value, i.e. 0.57. After this, the R_F gradually increases with an increase in the mole fraction. In case of L-hydroxyproline and DL-aspartic acid, the R_F value sharply decreases when the mole fraction of acetone attains a value 0.69. Beyond this, L-hydroxyproline shows sharp increase in R_F (0.70) whereas DL-aspartic acid shows a very slight increase.

For majority of amino acids, the R_F vs mole fraction plots are straight lines. Surprisingly, there is no effect of size or the nature of side-chain and functional groups present in various amino acids on the slope of these lines. Thus for DL-2-aminobutyric acid, L-leucine, DL-nor-leucine, DL-methionine, DL- β -phenylalanine, DL-tryptophan, DL-DOPA, L-cystine, L-glutamic acid, DL-alanine, L-tyrosine, DL-isoleucine and DL-threonine, the decrease in the R_F with an increase in the mole fraction of acetone may be due to the decrease in the polar nature of mobile phase composition. L-Hydroxyproline and L-proline show very low R_F particularly when mole fraction of acetone is 0.69. Contrary to the above, basic amino acids such as L-ornithine HCl, L-lysine HCl, L-histidine and L-arginine give lower R_F irrespective of mole fraction of acetone in the mobile phase used.

Effect of mole fraction of benzene : In case of acetone-benzene-acetic acid media having volume ratios 4 : 2 : 4, 4 : 3 : 3, 4 : 4 : 2 and 4 : 5 : 1, for majority of amino acids, the R_F value gradually decreases with an increase in the mole fraction of benzene except for DL-serine, DL-2-aminobutyric acid, DL-alanine, L-hydroxyproline, DL-methionine, DL-DOPA and DL-aspartic acid which exhibit a different behaviour. The decrease in R_F with increase in the mole fraction of benzene may be due to the increase in non-polar nature of the mobile phase. Further, DL-serine, DL-2-

aminobutyric acid and DL-alanine show maximum R_F when the mole fraction of benzene is 0.23, which is probably due to the higher solubility of these amino acids at this stage. L-Hydroxyproline, DL-methionine and DL-DOPA give a different zig-zag trend.

The basic amino acids, e.g. L-ornithine HCl, L-histidine, L-lysine HCl, and L-arginine exhibit a slight decrease in R_F value with an increase in the mole fraction of benzene. These amino acids give relatively lower R_F which may be due to their lower solubility in the given mobile phase.

Effect of mole fraction of acetic acid : For most of the amino acids, e.g. DL-alanine, DL-serine, L-leucine, DL-nor-leucine, DL-aspartic acid, L-glycine, DL-valine, DL-isoleucine, L-tyrosine, DL- β -phenylalanine, DL-tryptophan, L-cystine, L-glutamic acid, L-proline, DL-threonine, DL-2-aminobutyric acid, L-lysine HCl, L-histidine HCl and L-ornithine HCl, in acetone-benzene-acetic acid media in volume ratios 4 : 5 : 1, 4 : 4 : 2, 4 : 3 : 3 and 4 : 2 : 4, the R_F value initially increases with an increase in the mole fraction of acetic acid. It may be due to an increase in the polarity of the mobile phase. For some of the amino acids, e.g. DL-valine, DL-isoleucine, L-tyrosine, DL- β -phenylalanine, DL-tryptophan, L-cystine, L-glutamic acid, L-proline, L-cysteine HCl and DL-serine, almost ten-fold increase in R_F is in the mole fraction range 0.25–0.38.

However, few amino acids such as DL-serine, DL-methionine, DL-DOPA, L-hydroxyproline and L-arginine show irregular behaviour which may be attributed to the difference in their solubility in the given mobile phase. For basic amino acids such as L-ornithine HCl, L-lysine HCl and L-histidine, there is very slight increase in R_F with a five-fold increase in the mole fraction of acetic acid.

Conclusion : On the basis of R_F data, the solubility sequence of amino acids in butanol is predicted. The R_F values of amino acids having aliphatic side-chains are directly proportional to the size of the chains. The same is true in case of the heterocyclic neutral amino acids. This is quite in agreement with the earlier observations made on cellulose phosphate papers and stannic tungstate layers^{7,8}.

In butanol-acetic acid media, the basic amino acids have low R_F values than those of the neutral and acidic amino acids for which R_F is generally higher and remains almost constant in the pH range 0.0–1.0 but becomes less than 0.2 at pH 6.74. Further, for the basic amino acids the R_F lies be-

tween 0.6 and 0.8 at very low pH, i.e. in pure acetic acid media.

Some of the amino acids exhibit typical behaviour when the mole fraction of acetone lies in the range 0.57–0.69. For most of the amino acids, the R_F gradually decreases with an increase in the mole fraction of benzene. In acetone-benzene-acetic acid media, acetic acid is most effective for some of the amino acids when its mole fraction lies between 0.25 and 0.38. For the basic amino acids very slight increase in R_F is noticed even when there is five-fold increase in the mole fraction of acetic acid.

Experimental

Amino acids (Loba) and silica gel G (E. Merck) were used. All other solvents used were of A.R. grade (Qualigens). Test solutions and detectors were prepared as reported earlier⁸.

Preparation of chromatoplates and procedure for chromatography were the same as reported earlier⁹.

The amino acids were chromatographed in the following nineteen solvent systems used as mobile phases : (a) butanol-acetic acid in the proportions 10 : 0, 9 : 1, 8 : 2, 7 : 3, 6 : 4, 5 : 5, 4 : 6, 3 : 7, 2 : 8, 1 : 9, 0 : 10 and (b) acetone-benzene-acetic acid in the proportions 4 : 5 : 1, 4 : 4 : 2, 4 : 3 : 3, 4 : 2 : 4, 5 : 1 : 4, 6 : 1 : 3, 7 : 1 : 2 and 8 : 1 : 1.

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